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Rabindranath Tagore's *Where the Mind Is Without Fear* and Vasant

Bapat's: *जिथे न भीती शिवे मनाला*: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Translation Studies has acquired the status of an independent discipline and achieved the significant position in an academic and intellectual area. There is a scope for translation in the multi-linguistic and multi-cultural country and society. There are multiple career opportunities in the field of translation and interpretation. Rabindranath Tagore from Bengal and Vasant Bapat from Maharashtra are recognized as eminent literary figures in their regions. Both belong to different regions and cultures. It is significant to note here that these differences do not hamper the common thread of their poetic mind-set and creativity. The poem *Where the Mind Is without Fear* was originally written by Tagore in Bengali and he himself translated it into English. Vasant Bapat translated the English poem into Marathi entitled " *जिथे न भीती शिवे मनाला* " The present paper attempts to focus on the similarities of their writings and tries to analyse the both. The poems linguistically point out that culture and language cannot be barriers for translation.

Keywords: translation, regional culture, comparative, analysis.

Introduction:

In the postmodern period and the age of technology, the world has come closer. As a result, cluster and clash of one culture with the other is obvious. Each country nowadays experiences a phase of multilingualism. Consequently, in a multilingual country like India, translation becomes inevitable. Obviously, translation and a translator have a wide scope in the present scenario. Generally, the word translation evokes the impression that translation from other foreign language to the Indian language. But within a country itself, there is a vast scope for translation. A translation not only converts a book into another language, but a culture from one state, region, or country to another. It helps one to understand the other culture. Translation always offers a scope for the creativity of a translator, but it is significant to note that it is a difficult task, and challenging one. A translator has to acquire certain qualities and abilities. A good translator must have mastery over both the languages, the Source Language, i.e.. Language of the origin book and the Target Language i. e. language in which the book is to be translated, because each language has its own meaning, beauty, flavour and variety. The culture plays a vital role in the enrichment of language and literature.

What is Translation:

As Wikipedia defines, 'Translation is the communication of the meaning of a source-language text using an equivalent target-language text. The Oxford Dictionary defines translation as 'The process of translating words or text from one language into another.' Translation is a discipline that is related to a wide variety of other disciplines, such as Sociology, Linguistics, and Comparative and Cultural Studies etc.

Bapat refers Dryden's quotation in his book *Taulanik Sahityabhayas*. It says:

All translation, I suppose, may be reduced to three heads; first, that of metaphase, or turning an author's words word by word, and line by line, from the original language into another. . . The second way is that

of paraphrase, or translation with latitude, where the author is kept in view by the translator, so as never to be lost But his words are not so strictly followed as his sense, and that too is admitted to be amplified, but not altered. . . The third way is that of imitation, where the translator (if now he has not lost that name) assumes the liberty not only to vary from the words and sense, but to forsake them both as he sees occasion and taking only some general hints from the original, to run division on the groundwork, as he pleases. . . (Bapat, 50-51)

Among these, a literary translation is a challenging one as the translator has to understand not only the language but meaning of each word in socio-cultural context because lexical meaning changes according to the socio-cultural scenario. Content centred translation is easier than linguistic translation. Content centred translation is easily understood by the readers. In literary translation, words, phrases, grammar and content are always taken into consideration. A translator has to struggle a lot for the perfect shade of a word. In other words, a translator has to disguise or transgress himself in the original work.

There is a wide scope for translation in our country. A variety of languages lead a diversity of literature on various topics and issues in India. The literature of one state or the other state within the same country itself is a good option for translators. It enriches regional identities, cultural consciousness, and national integrity.

Rabindranath Tagore was a Bengali poet, artist, playwright, novelist, and a composer whose work has influenced Bengali literature. He was Asia's first Nobel laureate who won the 1913 Nobel Prize in literature for his *Geetanjali* which was initially written in Bengali, was translated by the poet Rabindranath Tagore himself in *Song Offerings* (1912). His poems are meditative, thought-provoking, and full of patriotism. The nation, India, salutes him for his song *Jana Gana Mana* by accepting it as the national anthem. His work *Naiwadya* (1901)

was famous for his Bengali poems, which are philosophical and devotional as well. He wrote poetry under the titles *Gitanjali*, *Gitali*, *Gitmala*, *Kheya* (1906) and *Naiwadya* (1901). The poems are highly devotional expressing the Cult of Indian Culture, and represents himself as the instrumental in Eastern philosophy.

Rabindranath Tagore's poem "*Where the Mind is Without Fear*" is included in *Gitanjali (Song Offerings)*. The poem was originally published in 1910. Tagore translated this poem into English in 1912. *Where the Mind is without Fear* is the best example of his patriotic and devotional feelings and mindset. Though the poem talks of patriotism, it has Tagore's spiritual touch. It makes the poem readable and has gained popularity among readers. *Where the Mind is without Fear* has musical tone and simplicity in diction and language. The poem is written in the pre-independence era of the nation.

Tagore's poem is a representation of every Indian who visualizes the Freedom of India, additionally, is a feeling of every citizen who has an urge to his country's freedom. In that sense, it breaks all the shackles of language. The vision of an independent country is perfectly highlighted through every word of the poem. The optimistic tone highlights the poem. Though it is Translated from Bengali, it never loses its beauty and theme. It appeals as if it is as the original one, and its credit goes to the poet himself.

A good translation is not only a journey from one language to another language but it is a dialogue between the two cultures as well. Tagore's *Where the Mind is without Fear* tempts any sensitive poet to translate. It is in his or her language. Vasant Bapat (1922-2002), the great Marathi poet and a critic translated it into Marathi. Though Tagore and Vasant Bapat belong to the same country, India, has regions and cultures that differ. As the translator, Vasant Bapat successfully maintains the flow of thought of the original writer and the poem too. He never disturbs its melody, rhyming, and diction too. Tagore's poem consists

of sixteen lines which has no stanza pattern. The translator Vasant Bapat maintains the lines of the poem, but he breaks the poem in four stanzas with four lines in each stanza.

Tagore writes:

Where the mind is without fear and
the head is held high:
where the knowledge is free:

Vasant Bapat translates it as:

जिथे न भीती शिवे मनाला
जिथे न राहती ताठर माना
शब्द जिथे सत्यातून जन्मे
तिथे न पडते बंधन ज्ञाना

Vasant Bapat, as the translator, takes the liberty to expand Tagore's idea and deliberately rhymes the 2nd and the 4th lines *माना* and *ज्ञाना*. However, he never diverts from the original idea of Tagore but explores it in detail. It seems that Tagore's dream of a free country is effectively brought out by Vasant Bapat. Sometimes a translator surpasses the imagination of the original writer. The above four lines are the best illustration of the same..

Tagore carries his vision of independent India in the next four lines as:

Where the world has not been broken
Up into fragments by narrow domestic walls;
Where words come out from the depths
Of truth;
Where tireless striving stretches its arms
Towards perfection

Tagore here dreams of a golden age and hopes that a free nation will be free from the shackles of religion, castes, creed, region, and language. The people in The country will enjoy freedom in a free nation. He expects his free nation should not be divided for any reason. Tagore's lines have come out of rage As he is a witness to the Indian freedom struggle movement under the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi. Tagore's lines express his concern for the free India. Tagore was, as described by S.K. Ghose, '...a human poet and an honest poet' (Prasad 30). Tagore uses apt adjectives to express his dream of ideal free nation. He values the truth and the perfection, and expects his nation should strive for that.

Though Tagore's poem is written in big lines and length, it never breaks the continuity of thought, which appeals to the readers. Vasant Bapat also catches the same nerve of Tagore and translates the above lines as:

यतीकुळांचे तट हे लटके
जिथे जगाचे करिती न खंड
भगिरथाची अविरत गंगा
पूर्णत्वाला जाय अखंड

Here, Tagore's six lines are perfectly translated by Bapat only in four lines. The selection of the words, their melody, and their rhyme is attractively utilized by Bapat. Moreover, he brings the Indian scripture to point out the poet's meaning of 'perfection' and 'tireless efforts'. These two words rightly brought into light the word *bhagirath* (*भगिरथ*). This is a fine example of Bapat's skill of translation as he never loses the original meaning of Tagore's exact emotions.

Bapat's use of the word '*yatikulanche tat*' (*यतीकुळांचे तट*) for Tagore's 'domestic walls'

expresses its depth of meaning effectively. As the translator, Bapat's mastery over his language, Marathi, as well as his depth of understanding of the original. The poem and his mindset in choosing the specific word are worth appreciating.

Tagore's further lines-

Where the clear stream of reason has not lost
its way into the dreary desert
Sand of dead habits;

Bapat translates these lines as-

शुध्द मतीचा झुळझुळणारा
जिथे वाहती निर्भर निर्झर
जड रूढींच्या मरुभूमीत
कधी न सुकती त्यांचे पाझर

In the ideal world of Tagore, he describes that people in his country must strive to enrich their wit, and they should be motivated by logic. People must test everything logically rather than emotionally. Bapat uses the words '*jad rudhinchya*' (जड रूढींच्या) for Tagore's 'dreary desert sand of dead habit', which is a more simplified version than the original one. Here the translator exactly points out Tagore's idea in selected words.

As the poet, Bapat's knowledge of language and his ability to use it are focused in the second line of this stanza. He uses the words '*nirbhar nirzar*' (निर्भर निर्झर) which are examples of alliteration. Tagore also expresses alliteration in the line 'dreary desert'. Thus, Bapat goes close to Tagore in his usage of diction. He expresses his ability in translation, his mastery over the language. Moreover, Bapat succeeds in capturing the exact mood of Tagore's poem. In Tagore's lines, we come across only alliteration, but Bapat's four lines cover three different

figures of speech, i.e., onomatopoeia as reflected in the words '*zulzulnara*' (झुळझुळणारा) alliteration in '*nirbhar nirzar*' (*निर्भर निर्झर*) and rhyme in '*nirbhar*' and '*pazar*' (*निर्भर पाझर*).

The last four lines of the poem-

Where the mind is led forward by
Thee into ever-widening thought and action-
Into that heaven of freedom, my Father,
Let my country awake.

Tagore prays from his bottom of the heart that his nation should follow the path of progress where the thought and action go hand in hand. The nation will be free not only from the British rules but also from the evils in society. He hopes that the nation should strive for a wide horizon. He prays to God and appeals He has to fulfill his dream of a free, independent ideal nation. The poet is optimistic for the change he visualizes for his free country.

Bapat's translation for these lines:

तुझी प्रेरणा जिथे मनाला
सदा विकासी करिते ईशा
स्वातंत्र्याच्या स्वर्गी प्रभू
जागृत करी तू माझ्या देशा

Like Tagore, Bapat's last stanza is also an appeal to God. He successfully attracts readers to the last two lines, which are the perfect translations of Tagore's original two lines. Bapat, as the translator, uses his imagination in the second line of this stanza. Though this line does not exactly match with Tagore's second line brings the exact meaning of the line.

Translation, especially of poetry, is rarely handled because, as a translator, one has to pay minute details of its rhyme, metre, diction, figure of speech, prosody, etc. Besides, a translator is not supposed to deviate from the central idea and its beauty. He is expected to

maintain the emotional appeal of the original poem. As a result, very few poets succeeded in translating the poem meaningfully.

Vasant Bapat's attempt to translate Tagore's poem *Where the Mind Is Without Fear* is, in that sense, a successful one. He has studied an original poem in detail. Of course, he has violated the form of a poem, but it does not affect the poem's mood, tone, content, meaning, and theme. His creativity and scholarship lies there. He has successfully maintained the national, emotional and the spiritual atmosphere of the poem. In that sense, like Tagore's poem. Bapat's translation can also be treated as a masterpiece of translation and literature.

Conclusion:

It is rightly said that a good translation is not only a journey from one language to another, but also it is a dialogue between two cultures. Bapat's translation proves Dr. Johnson's statement that 'poetry can not be translated' and Robert Frost's remark that 'poetry is that which is lost in translation' is wrong. An able, intellectual translator gives justice to his or her translation. Thus, the two literary masterpieces from the two eminent literary figures from two different regions, languages, and cultures have given a literary intellectual treat to their readers.

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